

COOPERATION OF OPERATIONAL UNITS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST TERRORISM: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Qodirov Doniyor Baxtiyorovich

self-employed applicant

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14172548>

Abstract. The article reveals the specifics of the interaction of the units of the operational search service of the internal affairs bodies in the fight against terrorism. The problems of interaction of the internal affairs bodies with other branch services, law enforcement agencies and members of the public in the fight against terrorism by units of the operational search service and ways to overcome them are indicated. National and international legal acts regulating the fight against terrorism are analyzed.

Keywords: operational-search service, fight against terrorism, internal affairs bodies, operational-search activities, operational-search activities, operational-search service units, departmental interaction, regulatory legal acts.

Cooperation of operational units in the field of countering terrorism is carried out in accordance with a number of legislative acts. In particular, in accordance with the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" the internal affairs bodies carry out their activities in accordance with to interact with the self-government bodies of citizens, other organizations and citizens, as well as the media and interact with law enforcement agencies of other states and international organizations on issues related to their competence, in accordance with legislative acts and international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

In accordance with the Law "On Counteracting Terrorism" government bodies, local government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions and organizations, officials, as well as citizens provide assistance and necessary assistance to state bodies, carrying out the fight against terrorism, and also provide assistance to foreign states of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of combating terrorism, to carry out their cooperation with law enforcement agencies, special services and international organizations in accordance with international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2].

In the agreements on mutual cooperation signed with foreign states, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, joint decisions and departmental acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs concluded with other law enforcement agencies, in order to increase the effectiveness of the measures defined in these documents, there is a need to

improve them and introduce modern information and communication technologies into this process [3].

Currently, there are 13 main UN international documents governing the fight against terrorism, and Uzbekistan ensures the timely implementation of all conventions and protocols in this direction.

In turn, the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and treaties adopted within the framework of regional organizations such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) aimed at combating religious extremism and terrorism, for example, the Shanghai Convention on Combating Terrorism, Separatism and Extremism (Shanghai, 15.06.2001). The location of the Anti-Terrorism Center within the SCO in Tashkent can be regarded as a recognition of the role of Uzbekistan in the fight against terrorism in the region [4].

In addition, Uzbekistan effectively cooperates with many countries of the world, including the United States, Russia, China, Turkey, India, Saudi Arabia, Iran and the republics of Central Asia, on the basis of bilateral treaties to combat international terrorism.

The fight against international terrorism, launched by the world community, has become increasingly acute. Therefore, the international security system should be determined by joint efforts coordinated at the interregional level, and not on the basis of geographical characteristics.

The head of our state touched upon several issues of increasing the efficiency of the SCO. Including:

First, today international terrorist groups and destructive forces use information technology for their malicious purposes, such as subjugating young people and spreading the idea of violence.

In this regard, we propose to empower the SCO to amend the constituent documents of the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure and establish a system for monitoring and countering threats arising in the global information space.

Secondly, it is necessary to strengthen joint concrete measures to prevent the involvement of the younger generation in the activities of various terrorist and radical structures.

In solving tasks in this direction, it is required to achieve a single agreement between the SCO member states within the framework of SCO summits, as well as the development of cooperation and the implementation of concrete practical measures with the relevant law enforcement agencies, as well as internal affairs bodies.

We believe that this cooperation is primarily related to the signing of memorandums between the internal affairs bodies of the SCO member states, units of the operational-search service, persons involved in terrorism, committed terrorist acts, creation of a unified information system that allows you to quickly receive and receive information about funds, which they use, about the persons put on the wanted list in this direction, as well as the organization of joint trainings aimed at equipping with technical means and improving the professional knowledge and skills of operational personnel. At the same time, conferences and trainings at various levels were held on the implementation of the signed bilateral and multilateral documents, specific mechanisms and practical joint actions aimed at combating terrorism were not implemented [5].

In our opinion, it is advisable to establish a mechanism for the exchange of information on persons participating in armed conflicts on the territory of other states as an urgent direction for improving cooperation in the fight against terrorism within the framework of the competent law enforcement agencies of member states of a certain international or regional organization.

At the same time, in the fight against terrorism, the units of the operational-search service carry out other sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, especially important is cooperation with the crime prevention service, the relevant departmental regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which determine the main tasks and responsibilities of employees in increasing the effectiveness of operational-search measures in this direction. There are topical issues related to the development and implementation of new orders, instructions and practical manuals.

In countering terrorism, it is important to increase the effectiveness of departmental interaction and coordination work, in accordance with the Law "On Countering Terrorism," coordinate the activities of state bodies involved in countering terrorism, as well as interact in preventing, identifying, suppressing and minimizing the consequences of terrorist activities, support is carried out by the State Security Service.

The fight against crime requires a set of measures. Thus, coordinated, systematic measures of state bodies and public organizations should be implemented in crime prevention. It can also be said that timely and full disclosure of crimes will help prevent other crimes in the future.

In accordance with the Law "On Countering Terrorism," state bodies engaged in the fight against terrorism, the State Security Service, the National

Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Security Service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the State Customs Committee, the Ministry of Defense, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the General Prosecutor's Office of the Legislative Chamber Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Articles 9-14 determine the powers of these bodies in the field of combating terrorism.

In accordance with this Act, in the course of examining the powers of state bodies to combat terrorism, we can see that none of them is entrusted with the authority to disclose terrorism, and in the context of the Act there are no norms related to the disclosure of terrorist activities in the fight against terrorism.

However, the fight against terrorism means not only the prevention, identification and suppression of terrorist activities, but also its disclosure.

In addition, when analyzing the regulatory legal acts of some foreign countries regulating countering terrorism, we see that most of them reflect some norms related to the disclosure of terrorism.

In particular, in order to suppress and disclose a terrorist act, minimize its consequences, protect the vital interests of the individual, society and the state in the Law of the Russian Federation "On Countering Terrorism," in accordance with article 12, part 2 of the legal regime of the counter-terrorist operation.

The Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Combating Terrorism" defines that "the fight against terrorism... activities of state authorities, local governments, organizations and institutions, regardless of ownership, to identify, prevent, suppress, disclose and investigate terrorist acts...". Similar norms are contained in the laws of other countries aimed at combating terrorism.

But at the same time, the orders and instructions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan define the forms, the subject of departmental interaction in matters of interaction and coordination with state security bodies (SGB) in the field of countering terrorism, the types of official documents covering the exchange of information, the timing of their execution and the implementation of activities in this area. Specific tasks and responsibilities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the SGB are not defined.

In our opinion, the adoption of joint departmental regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the State Security Service may affect the further effectiveness of the fight against terrorism in solving these issues in the fight against terrorism and increasing the effectiveness of operational-search activities in this direction.

Also, the presence of shortcomings in the interaction of the operational

units of the territorial bodies of internal affairs with the operational units of institutions for the execution of sentences in the fight against terrorism negatively affects the effectiveness of this work [6].

In our opinion, it is advisable to revise the mechanism for studying and strengthening interaction between the territorial bodies of internal affairs and the operational units of penitentiary institutions aimed at combating terrorism, as well as introduce measures to strengthen responsibility and accountability in this direction.

At the same time, it is important to improve the interaction of operational units of the internal affairs bodies with the crime prevention service, as well as the lack of proper study by the leaders of the facts of establishing interaction between operational units and crime prevention services in organizing and conducting this work.

In the fight against terrorism, individual preventive measures are important, which differ from other types of prevention in their priority.

Currently, the legal foundations of individual prevention and the procedure for its implementation are determined by the Law "On the Prevention of Offenses" and are widely used in the activities of the internal affairs bodies.

In particular, in this Law, in order to "prevent offenses - preserve and strengthen law and order, identify and suppress offenses, as well as identify and eliminate the causes of offenses and conditions conducive to "other measures".

Also, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 29, 2010 "On the prevention of neglect and offenses among minors" provides for "the timely identification of minors and families in a socially dangerous situation, as well as their socio-pedagogical rehabilitation and activities to prevent minors from committing offenses or other antisocial actions".

The purpose of individual prevention is to transform the consciousness of a person into a law-abiding citizen by positive correction, correcting his negative behavior against the laws of society. The main part of this work is carried out on the basis of cooperation between the operational units of the internal affairs bodies, law enforcement agencies and public organizations.

In our opinion, one of the main factors that have a negative impact on increasing the effectiveness of the fight against terrorism is the lack of systematic interaction of operational services with the internal affairs bodies when working with persons registered by operational units for committing terrorism-related offenses.

From the above, it can be concluded that in the effective organization of interaction between the operational units of the internal affairs bodies with other sectoral services, law enforcement agencies and the public in the fight against terrorism, it is important to improve organizational and tactical aspects and requirements in this direction.

It is especially important that operational units, together with the prevention service, have the knowledge and skills necessary for the thorough preparation and implementation of individual preventive measures.

Использованная литература:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 16, 2016 "On Internal Affairs Bodies" / /Newspaper "People's Word". No. 184 (6619) dated September 17, 2016.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of December 15, 2000 "On Countering Terrorism" // Vedomosti Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2001. No. 1-2, Art. 15.
3. Khodzhiev N.M., Irisbekov U.A. International legal framework for combating terrorism and extremism.
// Improving the activities of operational-search apparatus in the fight against terrorism and extremism: problems and solutions. Collection of scientific articles. - T. Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. Art. 206-121.
4. Khasanboev O. State and religious relations in Uzbekistan: religious organizations, trends, current directions of ideological struggle. T.: Tashkent Islamic University, 2014. - B. 216.
5. Zhumaev A.Zh. Uzbekistan's contribution to international application in countering terrorism // Combating terrorism as a transnational threat: Uzbekistan and world experience: Materials of the international scientific and practical conference. - T., 2015. - 5-9 s.
6. Irisbekov U.A., Turaev B.S. Organization of interaction of counterterrorism and extremism devices with other branch services of the Department of Internal Affairs in solving crimes in criminal cases related to terrorism and extremism. // Improving the activities of operational-search devices to combat terrorism and extremism: problems and solutions. Collection of scientific articles. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. Art. 163-169.

